

The Effect of Academic and Non-academic Factors on Trainee Satisfaction and Reputation of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar)

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Abstract

The purposes of this study are to analyze the influence of academic factors on the trainee satisfaction, to explore the influence of non-academic factors on the trainee satisfaction, and to examine the effect of trainee satisfaction on reputation of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). To achieve these objectives, both primary and secondary data are used. Descriptive and analytical methods are applied in this study. Simple random sampling method is used in this study. One-month survey is conducted to collect the primary data. In this study, total population size is 334 trainees who are attending the Postgraduate Diploma in Civil Service Management Course Batch 8. According to the Raosoft sample size calculator, sample size is 179 trainees. This study finds that academic factors such as learning experience, teaching, and assessing have positively influenced on trainee satisfaction. The non-academic factors such as library services and student affairs have a positive influence on trainee satisfaction. Furthermore, there is a positive effect of trainee satisfaction on the reputation of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). Based on the results, the study recommends that the Executive Committee of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) should focus and enhance the academic factors such as learning experience, teaching, and assessing. In addition, the Executive Committee of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) should also consider enhancing the library services and student affairs as non-academic factors. By upgrading these academic and non-academic factors, trainee satisfaction will increase more. Trainee satisfaction will lead to building up the reputation of the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar).

Keywords: *Academic Factors, Non-academic Factors, Satisfaction, Reputation2*

1. INTRODUCTION

Better service quality yields higher student satisfaction, which leads to the formation of a good reputation. Ali et al. (2016) revealed that student satisfaction is influenced by many factors, including academic and non-academic factors and effective communication between students and faculty. Furthermore, Ali et al. (2016) also found that student satisfaction affects university image significantly, and that satisfied students perceive the institutional image positively.

The manpower of the government servants pushes a country to develop and grow sustainably forever. If the standard of performance of civil servants is not ensured, nations cannot make any headway in development. The government servants are included in the important sectors to develop and sustainably the country. The development of the country

depends on the qualities and abilities of the civil servants. Therefore, developing the ability of civil service officials is the core of all public sectors and the role of civil service personnel of a nation is very important. All around development of a nation mainly depends on government employees who are good hearted and competent and have a correct view and moral convictions.

Thus, the Government of Myanmar must recruit the new employees and then, give them training to know more about the process of government works. Training includes the usage of formal and informal processes to impart knowledge and support people acquire the skills needed for them to complete their jobs pleasingly, while progress makes employees for other positions in the organization and raises their capability to move into jobs that may not yet exist. As The new employee who are gazette officer plays a crucial role to serve the public effectively and to build the Nation.

Therefore, in Myanmar, various training courses are always conducted at all ministries and departments. Civil servant of all ministries and departments in Myanmar conducts training at the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) and (Upper Myanmar) under the supervision, control and guideline of Union Civil Service Board (UCSB) to become a good civil service personnel. Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) [CSA(LM)] conducting various training including new gazette officers training and in-service officers and staff of civil servants of all ministries and departments in Myanmar under the supervision of Union Civil Service Board [UCSB]. The new gazette officers training course is very important not only for their organization, but also for the entire nation and entire society.

Thus, this study focuses on the new gazette officers who attending the course of Postgraduate Diploma in Civil Service Management (PGDCSM) Batch 8 at the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). The study aims to analyze the influence of academic factors on the trainee satisfaction of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar), to explore the influence of non-academic factors on the trainee satisfaction of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) and to examine the effect of trainee satisfaction on reputation of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar).

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The academic refers to the main tasks and functions of academic staffs, which are transmitting of knowledge through research. Academic factors are described as academic responsibilities, which include teaching, conducting examinations, and assessing (Abdullah, 2006). Academic staff is evaluated for professionalism, competence, performance, and willingness to assist students. Greimel and Geyer (2003) observed that students need teachers to explain new learning content and provide answers clearly and comprehensibly. The academic staff's quality of service and their interaction with students are related to retention rates and student satisfaction (Khoo et al., 2017). Academic aspects/factors include positive attitudes, good communication skills, sufficient consultation, regular feedback to students and outsourcing teaching staff's ability of which relate to the responsibilities of academics (Firdaus, 2005). Descriptive criteria for this factor are related to academic issues such as knowledge, 3 teaching methods, problem solving in learning, communicative attitudes of

teacher towards learners (Abdullah, 2006). Academic factors including teaching, assessing, and learning experiences are described as academic responsibilities providing by the lecturing and institution.

Non-academic factors such as students' confidence, self-motivation, finances, social support, family support, and some researchers would say the most essential non-academic factor is social integration. This factor consists of indicators related to assisting students in satisfying their learning obligations and related to service delivery procedures, working hours, academic counselling, health care, finance, extracurricular activities, etc. These activities are the responsibility of students without direct teaching and learning activities (Abdullah, 2006). Non-academic factors include social life quality (i.e., student and psychological health counseling), admissions, financial services, cafeterias, library services, and other services not directly related to teaching and learning activities (Abdullah, 2006). The capability and willingness of the administrative staff and other service providers regarding respect for the other parties (eg. customer, student), equal treatment, and protection of the confidentiality of information are focused (Abdullah, 2006). Non-academic factors including student affairs, recreation and library services are supporting by the administrative department and staff.

Satisfaction in the context of graduate education has been defined as positive feelings that students have toward their program. An individual's level of satisfaction is dependent on the degree to which a service, experience, or product meets an individual's expectations. If a person's expectations have been met or exceeded, the individual is considered satisfied (Cacioppo, 2000). Trainee (student) satisfaction is a cognitive or affective reaction to a single or prolonged set of services that trainee (student) encounter (Ali et al., 2016). Trainees' (students') satisfaction not only plays a significant role in building image and reputation of the university it also contributes substantially to the attainment of educational goals (El Ansari & Oskrochi, 2006).

In higher learning industry, trainees (students) are the major customer for universities, which means success or failure of an institution is largely depends on its student satisfaction. Sapri et al. (2009) mentioned that trainee's (student's) satisfaction is a short-term attitude that results from evaluation of their experience on education services that they had received. Trainee (student) satisfaction as higher education trainees (customers) is very important to be assessed since the quality of a higher education institution can be seen from the level of student satisfaction (Yang et al., 2013). Satisfaction is thus based on the ability of a service provider to meet or surpass the expectations of a trainee (customer) (Rezaei et al., 2011). Satisfaction happens in higher education when perceived performance meets or exceeds the trainee's (student's) expectations, which is being shaped continually by repeated experiences in campus life (Firdaus, 2005).

Reputation refers to the positivity or negativity of an institution's image, which comes to the consumer's mind when viewing a brand (Lahap et al., 2016). Accordingly, a high reputation can offer certain advantages to an organization, such as obtaining better resources and hiring more competent staff, ultimately resulting in greater profitability opportunities

(Pfarrer et al., 2010). The reputation of an educational institution is a major element for customers; as every customer seeks to evaluate the overall positive impact of a product or service before taking purchase decision (Archambault, 2008). Reputation relates to the professional image projected by the university and the employment of the institutional graduates (Firdaus, 2005).

Figure1: Conceptual Framework of Kagasheki(2015)

Figure2: Conceptual Framework of Moslehpour et al. (2020)

Figure 3: Conceptual Framework of This Study (2022)

3. METHODOLOGY

This study of a simple random sampling method was used with questionnaires into the Postgraduate Diploma in Civil Service Management (PGDCSM) Course 8th Batch at Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). There were 8 batches of Postgraduate Diploma in Civil Service Management (PGDCSM) courses within 6 years. However, this study focused on only the 8th batch because I can't easily contact the trainees from the rest of the 7 batches. This study had a limited time frame for data collection. The target area is very specified; therefore, this study collected data from 179 trainees who attended the 8th batch of PGDCSM in Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar).

Data collection period started 1st July 2022 to 31st July 2022. According to the Raosoft sample size calculator app., sample size is 179 trainees out of the population size 334 trainees. The survey method is used to collect data from the targeted respondents through

distributing the questionnaire as a survey instrument. As a primary data, structured questionnaire with a 5-points Likert scale was developed. Secondary data were collected from previous research paper, textbooks, websites, and other related information resources from Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). After conducting survey, gathered data are summarized and then analyzed by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) Software. Descriptive method and multiple linear regression method were used for data sampling.

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents

Description		Number of Respondents (179)	Percentage (100%)
Gender	Male	61	34.08
	Female	118	65.92
Age Group (Years)	20-25	25	13.97
	25-30	117	65.36
	30-35	27	15.08
	35-40	9	5.03
	40 years and above	1	0.56
Educational Qualifications	Master's degree	45	25.14
	Bachelor's degree	134	74.86

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Table 2: The Effect of Academic Factors on Trainee Satisfaction

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t value	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	0.370	0.315		1.174	0.242	
Teaching	0.225*	0.103	0.176	2.172	0.031	2.129
Assessing	0.192*	0.105	0.148	1.826	0.070	2.134
Learning Experience	0.484**	0.105	0.425	4.598	0.000	2.770
R Square	0.461					
Adjusted R Square	0.452					
F Value	49.983 ***					
Durbin - Watson	1.619					

Source: Survey Data (2022). *** significance at 1% level. ** significance at 5% level. * significance at 10% level

Table 3: The Effect of Non-Academic Factors on Trainee Satisfaction

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t value	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	1.403	0.320		4.383	0.000	
Student Affairs	0.320***	0.089	0.275	3.610	0.000	1.431
Recreation	-0.083	0.085	-0.080	-0.969	0.334	1.680
Library Service	0.451***	0.083	0.419	5.464	0.000	1.451
R Square				0.292		
Adjusted R Square				0.280		
F Value				24.025***		
Durbin - Watson				1.565		

Source: Survey Data (2022), *** significance at 1% level, ** significance at 5% level, * significance at 10% level

Table 4: The Effect of Academic Factors and Non-Academic Factors on Trainee Satisfaction

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t value	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	0.143	0.322		0.443	0.658	
Academic	0.850***	0.099	0.612	8.548	0.000	1.660
Non-Academic	0.129	0.096	0.096	1.345	0.180	1.660
R Square				0.457		
Adjusted R Square				0.451		
F Value				74.197***		
Durbin - Watson				1.503		

Source: Survey Data (2022), *** significance at 1% level, ** significance at 5% level, * significance at 10% level

Table 5: The Effect of Trainee Satisfaction on Reputation of Civil Serviced Academy (Lower Myanmar)

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t value	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	0.671	0.206		3.261	0.001	
Student Satisfaction	0.833***	0.051	0.775	16.314	0.000	1.000
R Square				0.601		
Adjusted R Square				0.598		
F Value				266.147***		
Durbin - Watson				1.797		

Source: Survey Data (2022), *** significance at 1% level, ** significance at 5% level, * significance at 10% level

5. SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Understanding trainee satisfaction for academic and non-academic factors through the training course has become challenges for Executive Committee of the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). According to the findings mentioned above, academic factors is the most important factors among trainees in Postgraduate Diploma in Civil Service

Management Course Batch 8 at Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). And working on the factors affecting the trainee to satisfy the training course will help the Executive Committee of the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) to gain the competitive edge.

Regarding the academic factors, most of the trainee perceived that the institute provide the great academic factors during the training period. For getting more satisfy on academic factors, Executive Committee of the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) should try to get more knowledgeable and expert lecturers for teaching sectors and try to enhance the existing capacity of the lecturers such as Training of Trainer (ToT) in local and international. In assessing factors, internationally applied training assessing models should be added and applied, and transparent assessing models between lecturers and trainees must be made. Executive Committee need more aware, it is necessary to identify the training needs of the trainees, open the necessary courses, and make different course contents according to the position level and willingness of the trainee.

In the learning experience, students get knowledge from different programs, lessons, interaction with other people, or other experiences in which learning takes place. It can take place in conventional academic settings like in a classroom at schools or nonconventional environments which take place outside school locations or we can say outdoor environments. As all know students can get great learning experiences from both school and outside. Therefore, students should be motivated to participate in different school activities and the activities which take place outside the school premises.

The learning experience should be good for the students, they should like learning more and more daily. Students learn different things daily from teachers, they should be encouraged by the teachers to improve their skills from what they learn. They should know how to apply their learning experience in their daily activities. Students should know how to take advantage of the things they learn every day. It enhances value to the learner; this means teachers help them comprehend something they were not able to do before. The entire occasion should feel purposeful and put the necessities of the student first. Thus, positive significant effect on academic factors such as teaching, assessing and learning experience are contributed to get more perceived value of trainees. Executive Committee of the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) should emphasize and enhance these factors to increase trainee perceived value to get trainee satisfaction.

Non-academic factors also contribute to trainee satisfaction. Executive Committee needs to support more staffs in student affairs sections. It is also necessary to increase the training fee for accommodation and catering. Moreover, Executive Committee should focus and arrange well established in physical fitness and sports equipment and free Wi-Fi internet connection in each hostel and should schedule enough leisure time for sports and leisure 7 activities and off-campus cultural and recreational opportunities such as short field trip, sports and entertainment activity. It shows that the Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) care their trainees and this, in turn, will increase trainee satisfaction towards the training and the institute.

This study has considered only for trainee behavior on academic and non-academic factors. In this study focused on only the Postgraduate Diploma in Civil Service Management Course Batch 8. Training programs and training methodology providing by the institute studies should be made in the further study. And then further study will be considered the comparison between the regular course and diploma course who are attending both the two types of training course conducting the institute. Moreover, the study will also extend to the other postgraduate diploma course and advanced diploma course for further research and new factors in the influencing factors rather than this study. During the pandemic situation, it was very difficult to collect data therefore; further study should be extending to get more data sources widely in future.

6. CONCLUSION

Civil service training matter is including one of the main sectors of a government in a country to develop and growth sustainably. The government servants are not only implementer for government as well as the hands of the government but also giver to serve for public as well as a provider for them. Moreover, the competences of the civil service personnel are very important for public (to give service), a government (to perform implement) and a country (to push ahead). Therefore, the government need to fill up the competences such as knowledge, skills, and attitude more and more that improve to the civil service personnel as the changes is always happened in time every fields newly to reach and can be competitive in global level.

Although this study found that the academic factors of teaching, assessing, and learning experience have significantly influence on trainee satisfaction, this study also found that non-academic factors such as student affairs and library services are significantly influence on trainee satisfaction during the training period. Thus, this study said that the Executive Committee of the institute are emphasis on not only the academic factors but also the non-academic factors of the institute.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the academic factors such as teaching, assessing and learning experience and the non-academic factors such as student affairs and library services have positive influence on trainee satisfaction, trainee satisfaction has positively influence on the reputation of Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar). This research points out that the current training courses are needed to get satisfaction, interesting, and improvement and practice experience and to be useful in jobs and life to the trainees. Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) is being supported as one of the government hands and is being born the good civil servants. Civil Service Academy (Lower Myanmar) is implementing to reach quickly to good governance and clean Government.

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